

DESIGN AND DEVELOPMENT OF A TOWABLE GRAVITY EVACUATION TOILET BOWSER FOR LIGHT AIRCRAFTS

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ABSTRACT

A toilet bowser is a special lavatory service cart designed to collect human wastes from aircrafts for final disposal into the airport sewage facility. The objective of the project is to produce a towable toilet bowser capable of providing adequate ground support service to commuter aircraft lavatory connections located at height from 0.8m to 2.5m above the ground level. Required information was obtained from the data of existing systems of similar usage. Design analyses of various parts were done to come up with an overall body dimension of 2743mm x 914mm x 914mm, with an operator height reach of 2370mm. Materials for the construction were selected from the lots, with particular attention places on their cost and availability locally. Standard components were selected to allow for interchangeability.

SIGNIFICANCE: The significance of the work is that it allows for a low cost gravity evacuation system with well-constructed chassis for efficient handling and maintenance of commuter aircraft lavatories.

KEYWORDS: Waste Collection Tank (WCT), Rinsing Water Tank (RWT), Dump Valve, Water Pump, Elevating/Lifting Work Platform (EWP), Top Cover Plate (TCP)

INTRODUCTION

The perusal of literatures brings home the fact that we have only fragmentary information on the subject of toilet as a private secluded place to help the body relieve its waste [Richet, 1913]. Planes like birds, are predisposed to the nature calls, gravity does the rest. The first toilets in airplanes were simple buckets. Information on early flushing system is not available, however aircraft's cabins were not pressurized and it was easy to open doors and windows to relieve the aircraft of human wastes.

Today and happily for people leaving close to the airports, or under flight paths, there is no more falling manure. However, planes still have to be purged of their smelly "unpaid load". Hence the need for special designed lavatory service carts to collect the waste for final disposal into the airport sewage facility. Such service cart is called bowser, which is the term for a vehicle used to replenish the fuel and water supplies of aircraft at an airfield or airport [Stewart & Stevenson, 2000]. Airline Human Waste is collected in tanks on board the aircraft. Toilet are serviced at each stop; emptied, flushed and then refilled to preset levels with a mixture of water and a colored, aromatic, quaternary ammonium bactericidal compound in water – sachets, so as to disguise the toilet content. The chemical compound liquefies solid materials and tissues. There are sophisticated aircraft lavatory systems available in the market that require huge capital to procure; such as the Vacuum Evacuation; self – propelled toilet car, having a vacuum pump at one end of the waste tank connected through a vacuum regulator, for the purpose of human waste evacuation from aircrafts. Also available, is the DAFA 3200 M, and DAFA 1500 M, gravity evacuation toilet bowsers, with built- in water pump aggregate mounted on a commercial Mercedes chassis with diesel engine.

METHODOLOGY

The approach for the design was through literature review, development of suitable system shape and size, consideration of the materials to be used, design of components and parts of the system, selection of final dimensions, cost analysis and finally, construction, assembly and testing of the bowser.

Design Analysis

The design of the towable toilet bowser consists of two separate and independent welded sheet steel tanks attached to the bowser's chassis. The top of the WCT is equipped with an inspection opening with a cover and a waste filler pipe to connect the waste hose. Emptying of tank is done through a dump valve located at the bottom with a slide valve operated over rods because of danger of splashing. A waste hose from the top of the WCT is connected to the toilet outlet of an aircraft and the human wastes collected through gravity evacuation. The RWT is equipped with an inspection opening on the top with a filler cap. A screwed joint at the bottom can be easily released if it becomes necessary to empty the tank completely. A convectional self propel water pump positioned in-between the two tanks enable water to be filled into the aircraft via high pressure water delivery hose, connected to the filling nozzle of the airplane. Steering mechanism consisting of a rotating plate, wheel assembly, front and rear solid shaft, steering bolt and a tow bar, to ensure accurate in train tracking, excellent maneuverability and precise positioning. The EWP located at the top of the bowser; consist of an operator's platform, a ladder and a support bar, capable of attaining a height of at least 2.0 meters to facilitate the handling of commuter aircraft types.

Design of Components

Design of the EWP

In designing the EWP, the principle of virtual work was employed due to its advantages as stated thus, "if a system of connected rigid bodies is in equilibrium, the total virtual work of the external forces applied to the system is zero for any virtual displacement of the system" (Lindkvist, 1990)

$$\sum F_x = 0, \sum F_y = 0, \sum MA = 0$$

Fig 2.2.1: Free Body Diagram of the EWP

If the load is placed on the platform, so that its total weight is supported by the ladder, we shall use the reactive force exerted by the support bar when inclined at $\theta = 60^\circ$ to the base, as the basis for our design; $a = 1.20\text{m}$, and $S = 1.10\text{m}$

$$\partial U = 0 : -W_D \partial y + F_{CD} \partial s = 0 \text{-----(1)}$$

To express ∂s similarly in terms of $\partial \theta$, we first note that by the cosine rule,

$$S^2 = a^2 + L_i^2 - aL_i \cos \theta \text{-----(2)}$$

$$F_{CD} = \frac{aW_D S \cos \theta}{aL_i \sin \theta} = \frac{W_D S (\cot \theta)}{L_i} \text{-----(3)}$$

$$F_{CD} = \frac{W_D S(\cot \theta)}{L_i} = \frac{(112.5 \text{ kg} * 9.81 \frac{\text{m}}{\text{s}^2}) * 1.10 \text{ m} * \cot 60^\circ}{0.961 \text{ m}} = 0.73 \text{ KN}$$

Hence, the reactive force exerted by the support bar on the main ladder to overcome 1104N load and dead weight of members is 0.73KN.

The design analysis of the effort arm

The effort arm was designed for opening and closing of the dump valve conveniently. Therefore, for rigidity, the material used for the effort arm was mild steel. The equation employed is (Sadhu Singh, 2003)

$$d_E = \left[\frac{32ELn}{\sigma b \pi} \right]^{\frac{1}{3}} \text{-----(4)}$$

$$d_E = \left[\frac{32 * 196 * 1.07 * 2}{\pi 220 * 10^6} \right]^{\frac{1}{3}} = 0.0269 \text{ m (26.9 mm)}$$

Hence, a diameter of 20mm is use for ease of fabrication and cost effectiveness.

Design analysis of the TCP

In this design, the TCP is required to adequately support the weight of at least four persons each with an average weight of 75 kg. A factor of safety of 1.5 is preferred for economy of manufacture. Therefore, designed dead weight $W_D = 1.5 (4 \times 75 \text{ kg}) = 450 \text{ kg} = 4414.5 \text{ N}$

The total load acting on the TCP is 5639.341 N, (EWP's weight inclusive) and is assumed to be uniformly distributed. Hence, the TCP is considered as a beam of uniformly distributed load.

Calculating the thickness of the TCP, the flexural formula was employed (Ryder, 1996)

$$\frac{\delta_{\max}}{y} = \frac{M_{\max}}{I} \text{-----(5),}$$

Where $y = \left(\frac{L}{2} \right)$ and $I = \frac{bt^3}{12}$

$$BM_{(\max)} = 2819.670 \left(\frac{1.829}{2} \right) - 3083.292 * 0.915 \left(\frac{0.915}{2} \right) = 1287.884 \text{ Nm}$$

From the flexural formula,
$$I = \frac{(BM_{\max} * t_s)}{2\delta_{\max}} = \frac{bt_s^3}{12}$$

Therefore,
$$t_s^2 = \frac{6 * BM_{\max}}{b\delta_{\max}} = \frac{6 * 1287.884}{1.829 * 110 * 10^6} = 3.841 * 10^{-5} m^2$$

Therefore,
$$t_s = \sqrt{3.841 * 10^{-5} m^2} = 6.197 * 10^{-3} m = 6.197 mm$$

Hence, a sheet thickness, t_s of 6.0mm is use for cost effectiveness and availability of sheet size.

Design analysis of the vertical support bars for the TCP and Frame

Total load to act on the supporting bars is 674.165kg Therefore, the weight on one vertical member =

$$\frac{674.165}{6} = 112.36 kg$$
. Selecting an angle iron of $L1 \frac{1}{2} \times 1 \frac{1}{2} in$ of thickness $\frac{1}{4} in$

To get the buckling load of the material (Ryder, 1996)

$$P_c = \frac{\pi^2 EI}{4L^2} \text{----- (6)}$$

Where, E = young modulus of the material ($200 \frac{GN}{m^2}$) for mild steel, I = Moment of inertia, L =

Length of bar, $P_c =$

Buckling load

$$P_c = \frac{\pi^2 EI}{4L^2} = \frac{\pi^2 * 200 * 10^9 * 5.79 * 10^{-8}}{4 * 1.067^2} = 26778.355 N$$

Since,
$$\text{mass} = \frac{\text{Force}}{g} = \frac{26778}{9.81} = 2729.70 kg$$

With less than 2729.70Kg load, the angle iron will not buckle. This buckling load is by far greater than the load supported by each member. Hence, an angle iron of $1 \frac{1}{2} \times 1 \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{1}{4}$ inches can be used safely for the supporting bars.

Selection and calculation of the thickness of the WCT & RWT

The best material for this purpose is one that has the following properties; very light, high strength and resistance to corrosion.

The strength of the steel sheet is $169 \frac{MN}{m^2}$ (Yield Value)

The design of the tanks involves selection of the right thickness of sheet, and the theory employed is the flexural formula of a pure bending.

Fig.2.2.5: Waste Collection Tank Sheet

In this case, the cover sheet is assumed to have an imaginary support at both ends and the liquid weight is applied on it in the form of a distributed load. For easy mathematical relation, the top and sides of the tank are removed as shown in fig.

2.2.5, with simple end supports.

For the flexural formula equation
$$\frac{\delta_{\max}}{y} = \frac{M_{\max}}{I} \text{ (Ryder, 1996)}$$

Since pressure in fluid increases with depth, it is evident that the weight of dissolved human waste acting on section C, is greater than those at section A and B. Thus section C precedes the design. Hence, the base of the WCT is considered to be a simply supported, uniformly loaded thick beam.

Bending moment = $\frac{wl^2}{8}$ ----- (7), at $x = \frac{l}{2}$ Where w = load/unit length

At the centre where bending moment is maximum; we have, $x = \frac{l}{2} = 0.381\text{m}$

Therefore,
$$BM_{\max} = \frac{wl^2}{8} = \frac{(564.188/0.762) * 0.762^2}{8} = 70.524\text{Nm}$$

$$I = \frac{BM_{\max} * t_p^3}{2\delta_{\max}} = \frac{Lt_p^3}{12}; \text{ Therefore, } t_p^2 = \frac{6 * BM_{\max}}{b * \delta_{\max}} = \frac{6 * 70.524}{0.762 * 77.5 \times 10^6} = 7.165 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^2$$

Therefore, $t_p = \sqrt{7.165 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^2} = 2.677 \times 10^{-3} \text{ m}$

Hence, a plate thickness, t_p of 3.0mm gauge is used for adequate strength.

Conductors sizing for flow rate of water pump requirement

The conductor used is plastic pipe because it does not corrode and has high resistance to a broad group of industrial chemicals (Thomas & Vierick, 1970). It does not support combustion, its non-magnetic and non-sparking; imparts no odor or taste to conductors, is light ($\frac{1}{2}$ the weight of aluminum), has low flow resistance, resists weathering. The pipe

is to handle a flow rate of 60 $\frac{L}{\text{min}}$ (or 15.82 gpm or $0.0001 \frac{m^3}{s}$). The maximum recommended velocity for pump suction lines is 1.2 m/s in order to prevent excessively low suction pressures and resulting pump cavitations (Anthony Esposito, 1980) Hence to obtain the minimum inside diameter that will provide an average fluid velocity of $1.2 \frac{m}{s}$; the minimum required pipe flow area is resolve from, V

$$\text{average} = \frac{Q}{A} \text{-----(8)}$$

$$\text{Therefore, } A \text{ (m}^2\text{)} = \frac{Q \left(\frac{m^3}{s} \right)}{v \left(\frac{m}{s} \right)} = \frac{0.0001 \left(\frac{m^3}{s} \right)}{1.2 \left(\frac{m}{s} \right)} = 8.33 \times 10^{-5} \text{ m}^2$$

$$A = \frac{\pi D_i^2}{4} \text{-----(9);}$$

$$D_i = \sqrt{\frac{4A}{\pi}} = \sqrt{\frac{4 * 8.333 \times 10^{-5}}{\pi}} = 0.0103 \text{ m}$$

Therefore the minimum inside diameter of the pipe to be used is 0.0103m (10.3 mm)
From the standard pipe sizes table (Anthony Esposito, 1980), the two smallest acceptable pipe sizes based on flow rate requirements are: -

Schedule 40: D_0 , 0.675 – in; 0.493 – in, D_i

Schedule 80: D_0 , 0.675 – in; 0.423 – in, D_i

Checking the two pipe sizes for appropriate working pressure

For the schedule 40:

$$\text{The wall thickness is given thus; } t = \frac{(D_0 - D_i)}{2} = \frac{(0.675 - 0.493)}{2} = 0.091 \text{ in}$$

The Burst pressure (fluid pressure that will cause the pipe to burst) is

$$BP = \frac{2tS}{D_i} \text{-----(10)}$$

$$BP = \frac{2 * 0.091 * 55000tS}{0.493} = 20304.26 \text{ psi}$$

The working pressure at which the pipe can safely operate is obtained thus;

$$WP = \frac{BP}{FS} \text{----- (11)}$$

Since the pressure of the water is on the low side, a factor of safety of 8 is recommended to ensure the integrity of the conductor by determining the maximum safe level of working pressure.

$$WP = \frac{20304.26}{8} = 2538.03 \text{ psi}$$

NOTE: Is $WP \geq$ system's operating pressure?

For the schedule 80:

The wall thickness is given thus; $t = \frac{(D_o - D_i)}{2} = \frac{(0.675 - 0.423)}{2} = 0.126 \text{ in}$

$$BP = \frac{2tS}{D_i} = \frac{2 * 0.126 * 55000}{0.493} = 32765.96 \text{ psi}$$

$$WP = \frac{BP}{FS} = \frac{32765.96}{8} = 4095.74 \text{ psi}$$

Both Working Pressures are greater than the system's operating pressure, hence, acceptable. For cost effectiveness, Schedule 40 pipe size is used.

Pressure head of water pump

Fig. 2.2.6: Piping/Conductor System of the Water Collection

DATA: The pump is adding 1 hp (746W) to the water; Pump flow is $0.0001 \frac{m^3}{s}$. The pipe has 0.0125m – inside diameter. The specific gravity of water is 1.0; the kinematic viscosity of water at 20°C is $1.01 \times 10^{-6} \frac{m^2}{s}$. The elevation difference between station (1) and (2) is 1ft (0.3048m). Writing Bernoulli's equation between stations (1) and (2);

$$Z_1 + \frac{P_1}{\gamma} + \frac{V_1^2}{2g} + H_p - H_m - H_L = Z_2 + \frac{P_2}{\gamma} + \frac{V_2^2}{2g} \text{ -----(12)}$$

Since there is no hydraulic motor between stations (1) and (2), $H_m = 0$, $V_1 = 0$ and $\frac{P_1}{\gamma} = 0$ (the water tank is vented to the atmosphere). Also, $Z_1 - Z_2 = 0.3048 \text{ m}$

Solving for V_2 :
$$V_2 \left(\frac{m}{s} \right) = \frac{Q \left(\frac{m^3}{s} \right)}{A \left(m^2 \right)} = \frac{1.0 \times 10^{-4}}{\left(\frac{\pi 0.0125^2}{4} \right)} = 0.815 \frac{m}{s}$$

Therefore, velocity head at station 2 is;
$$\frac{V_2^2}{2g} = \frac{0.815^2}{(2 * 9.81)}$$

The Reynolds number is thus;
$$N_R = \frac{\left[V \left(\frac{m}{s} \right) * D \left(m \right) \right]}{\nu \left(\frac{m^2}{s} \right)} = \frac{\left[0.815 * 0.0125 \right]}{1.01 \times 10^{-6}} = 10086.63 \approx 1.0 \times 10^4$$

Since the flow is turbulent (i.e. $10086.63 > 4000$), and relative roughness of plastic is considered smooth (Sullivan, 1989). On the N_R axis of the Moody diagram, the friction factor, f , is approximately 0.03.

The total length of the plastic pipe, $L_T = L_1 + L_{equivalent}$ $L_1 = 2.432$ m
 The equivalent length of the twelve 90° elbow fittings used along the stations is:

$$L_{equivalent} = 12 \left(\frac{K * D}{f} \right)_{90^\circ elbow}, \text{ (K-factor for } 90^\circ \text{ elbow} = 0.75)$$

$$= 12 \left(\frac{0.75 * 0.0125}{0.03} \right)_{90^\circ elbow} = 3.750 \text{ m}$$

Therefore, the total length of the plastic pipe, $L_T = 2.432 + 3.750 = 6.182$ m

→ From,
$$H_L = f \left(\frac{L_T}{D} \right) \frac{V_2^2}{2g} = 0.03 \left(\frac{6.182}{0.0125} \right) 0.0339 = 0.528 \text{ m}$$

Substituting the values obtained into the Bernoulli's equation, to solve for P_2/γ

$$\frac{P_2}{\gamma} = (Z_1 - Z_2) + H_P - H_L - \frac{V_2^2}{2g} = -0.1524 + H_P - 0.528 - 0.0339 = H_P - 0.5573$$

For the pump head, we have;

$$H_P = \frac{PumpPower(W)}{\left[\gamma \left(\frac{N}{m^3} \right) * Q \left(\frac{m^3}{s} \right) \right]} \text{-----(13)}$$

Specific weight, γ , of water at $20^\circ\text{C} = 9792.34 \frac{N}{m^3}$

Therefore,
$$H_P = \frac{745W}{\left[9792.34 \left(\frac{N}{m^3} \right) * 1.0 \times 10^{-4} \left(\frac{m^3}{s} \right) \right]} = 761.82 \text{ m}$$

Thus,
$$P_2 = \gamma_{water} * 761.27 = 9792.34 * 761.17 = 7.45 \text{ Mpa} = \underline{1081 \text{ psi}}$$
 Amadu

Design analysis of bowser's shaft

Shaft design consists primarily of the determination of the correct shaft diameter to ensure satisfactory strength and rigidity when the shaft is conveying motion under various operating conditions (Hall, Holowenko, Laughlin, 2002). The weight of the toilet bowser is supported by two shafts, with the front shaft forming the basis of the design since it bears more loads.

$$\text{Total mass acting on one shaft is} = \frac{1757.1964\text{kg} * 9.81\text{m/s}^2}{2} = 8619.046\text{N} = P$$

Taking moment about Ra ($M_a = 0$)

$$4309.523 (0.165) + 4309.523 (0.659) - R_b \times 0.824 = 0$$

Therefore, $R_b = 4309.523 \text{ N}$

But, $R_a = P - R_b = 4309.523 \text{ N}$ i.e. sum of vertical upward forces are equal to sum of vertically downward forces}

Torsional moment of the shaft

From the formula, torsional moment, $M_{\text{torsional}}$ is given as (Hall, Holowenko, Laughlin, 2002)

$$M_{\text{torsional}} = \frac{(1000 * 60 * KW)}{(\text{rev/min}) * 2\pi} = \frac{9550 * KW}{(\text{rev/min})} \text{-----(14)}$$

Since the shaft is not subjected to any revolution, hence torsional moment is zero

Diameter of the shaft

The diameter of the shaft is computed from the relationship given below (Hall, Holowenko, Laughlin, 2002).

$$d_s^3 = \left(\frac{16}{\tau}\right) \sqrt{(K_b M_b)^2 + (K_t M_t)^2} \text{----- (15)}$$

Where $K_b = 1.5$, $K_t = 1.0$, and $\tau = 55 \times 10^6 \text{ N/m}^2$ for shafts without key way

$$\text{Therefore, } d_s^3 = \left(\frac{16}{\pi * 55 \times 10^6}\right) \sqrt{(1.5 * 711.071)^2 + (1.0 * 0)^2}$$

$$\text{Therefore, } d_s = (9.877 \times 10^{-5})^{\frac{1}{3}} = 4.622 \times 10^{-2} \text{m} \approx 46.22 \text{mm}$$

Hence use 46.0mm diameter shaft, the nearest standard size and for ease of fabrications

Bearing / bushing design analysis

For this design, bushings were used to support the shafts, since the shafts are subjected to no rotational speed. The design of the bushing is based on the formula; $b_0 = 0.1 * d_s$ (Shingley & Mischke, 2001), where b_0 is the thickness of the bushing and d_s is the diameter of the shaft upon which the bushing is to be slotted on. A shaft diameter of 46.0 mm was adopted, $b_0 = 0.1 \times 46.0 = 4.6\text{mm}$

CONSTRUCTION, ASSEMBLY, TESTING AND COST ANALYSIS

Fabrication of the waste collection and rinsing water tanks

The tanks were fabricated by cutting galvanized steel material in accordance with the given specifications, and the edges of the various parts are then welded using Oxyacetylene gas welding to avoid leakage. The bottoms of both tanks were sloped towards the drain. Both tanks have at their top a leak proof – access holes of dimension 194mm x 192mm, to allow for cleaning and inspection. The RWT is equipped with a drain plug and a 1-inch filler cap.

Fabrication of the effort arm

The mild steel rod lever was turned to 20mm diameter with length 1070mm. A linkage mechanism was incorporated to facilitate the opening and closing of the dump valve, located at the bottom of the WCT. A standard 100mm (4 inches) Roylin-coupling with the necessary waste hose was incorporated to allow waste to flow by gravity into the WCT.

Fabrication of the top cover vertical support bars

The top cover vertical support bar was made from a standard angular iron of L1½ “x L1½ “of thickness ¼ “cut to specification, welded to the top cover member. The total length of each of the six support bars is 1.067m

The high-lift water pump system

This consists of a complete self-propelled water pump machine, plastic piping system, together with a high-pressure water delivery hose. A water pump of the following specification [0.5 hp (373 W) & 35 L/min] was adopted for cost effectiveness.

DISCUSSION AND TABULATION OF RESULTS

TABLE (1): Average Time of Discharge of Water from RWT

DESIGNATED HEIGHT / SCALE POINTS	TIME TO DISCHARGE THE TANK AT A PARTICULAR HEIGHT / (Minutes)	AVERAGE TIME OF DISCHARGE AT SCALE POINTS / (minutes)	TOTAL AVERAGE TIME OF DISCHARGE / minutes
A / 60 ⁰	(10.05)(9.25)(9.48)	10.00	10.11
B / 45 ⁰	(10.09)(9.15)(9.40)	9.55	
C / 30 ⁰	(10.09)(9.17)(9.47)	9.58	

TABLE (2): Result of Bowser’s Scale Point Height

S/No.	DESIGNATED HEIGHTS / SCALE POINT (m)	APPROXIMATE HEIGHT OF BOWSER (m)	APPROX. ADDITIONAL HEIGHT (m)	TOTAL HEIGHT OF LADDER FROM GROUND LEVEL (m)
1	A / 60 ⁰	1.33	1.04	2.37
2	B / 45 ⁰	1.33	0.85	2.18
3	C / 30 ⁰	1.33	0.60	1.93

Table 3: Cost analysis of the materials used

PARTS	MATERIAL / SIZE	QTY	UNIT RATE	COST
Rinsing water tank, & Waste collection tank	8ft x 4ft x 3mm thick sheet	3	N 5,500	N 16,500
Vertical support members, Shaft frame assembly & Tow bar	$1\frac{1}{2} \times 1\frac{1}{2} \times \frac{1}{4}$ Angle iron	6402mm, 0.5 full length & 1250mm	N 3,000	N 8,750
Horizontal members	$1\frac{1}{4} \times 1\frac{1}{4} \times \frac{1}{4}$ Angle iron	7314mm	N 2,750	N 2,750
Waste/Faeces hose	4 inches	2.5m	N 600	N 1,500
Discharge rod lever	20mm solid ext. diameter	330mm	N 1, 200	N 1,200
Base cover sheet	8ft x 4ft x 5mm steel sheet	1 full size	N 8,750	N 8, 750
Top cover sheet	8ft x 4ft x 5mm steel sheet	1 full size	N 8,750	N 8,750
Side cover sheet, & Step cover sheet	8ft x 4ft x 1.5mm Al. sheet	(3 full size) & (0.5m by 0.35m)	N 8,000	N 24,000 & (N 1,500)
Dump valve Outlet pipe	3 inches ext. diameter	1.5 inches	N 800	N 800
Bolts, Nuts & Washers	M10 x 1.25, & M12 x 1.25	30 pieces, 30 pieces	(N 4) & (N 10)	(N 120) & (N 300)
Electrode	Gauge 12	1 pack	N 800	N 800
Waste dump valve	Mild steel component	1	N 10,000	N 10,000
Water Pump	0.5 horse power	1	N25, 500	N25, 500
Water conductor	1 inch plastic pipes	1 full length	N 1,800	N 1,800
Conductor fittings/valves	Plastic & Metal types	12 pieces	N 50	N 600
Water delivery hose	1 inch ext. diameter hose	2.5 m	N 300	N 750
Vertical members, Horizontal members, Operator's compartment member	30mm x 30mm x 1.5mm	3full length	N 2,500	N 7,500
Front & Rear shaft	20mm ext. diameter (812mm length)	2	N 2,000	N 4,000
Tyres	Solid tyres	4	N 800	N 3,200
Steering bolt	32 mm diameter	1	N 90	N 90
Rotating plate	406mm x 483mm x 5mm	2	N 1,200	N 2,400
A Stop	20mm x 20mm x 1.5mm	1/3 full length	***	N 840
Towing eye	According to design	*****	*****	N 450
Water Roylin Coupling	Standard size (ISO / R 47)	1	N 18,000	N 18,000
Waste Roylin Coupling	Standard size (ISO / R 47)	1	N 35,000	N 35,000
Painting	****	****	****	23, 450
Total cost of Labour used	****	****	****	N 25, 000. 00 K
Overall cost of Production:	****	****	****	N 234, 300: 00K

Fabrication of the EWP

For the vertical rail members, cut out two square pipes of length 1.2m each and produce a bevel of 45° on one end of each pipe. To the other ends, attach a small length of circular steel pipe. For the platform support bar, cut out two square pipes of length 1.10m each and weld it to the operator's platform. For the operator's platform, cut out two square pipe of length 1.12m, 0.5m, 0.7m, and 0.35m each and assemble all together by way of welding as shown in figure 2.

Fabrication of the shafts

The shafts were fabricated using the lathe machine. Various operations such as cutting, centering, facing and chamfering were experienced while fabricating the shafts, to obtain the following shafts specifications: - Material: Mild steel; Length: 1002mm, & Diameter: 46mm. A bushing with the following specifications was force-fitted at the ends of the shafts before inserting it into the wheels.

Thickness: 4.6 mm; Inner diameter: 46.0 mm; Outer diameter: 55.2 mm

Fabrication of the tow bar

The tow bar was made long enough to prevent the toilet bowser and the towing tractor from contacting each other when turning at minimum swept radius. A stop was welded to the tow bar to prevent the towing eye from coming into contact with the ground when dropped.

ASSEMBLY

The procedure for assembling the toilet bowser is as follows

1. Weld the angle iron to produce the bed frame, attach the steering mechanism to the frame, after the tow bar was welded to the frame.
2. Put in place the constructed tanks on the bed frame.
3. Put in place the water pump in between the tanks and connect the plastic piping system to the RWT.
4. Bolt the top cover sheet to the horizontal support bars then bolt it to the vertical support bar. The EWP assembly is then bolted to the TCP.
5. Lubricate all the bushings and force fit them into position and smears reasonable quantity of grease (shell simnia or alvania BP grease) at the ends of the shafts.
6. Connect the water delivery pipe and the waste hose.
7. Fix the dump valve, effort arm and linkage assembly at the bottom of the WCT.
8. Paint the entire body of the assembled system to give it an attractive look and most importantly to minimize the effects of corrosion.

The assembled diagram is shown in figure 1

TESTING

From the field test, the waste hose from the waste tank was connected to waste outlet of the aircraft. Human wastes from the aircraft were collected, and left inside the WCT for 24 hours. After physical examinations of the tank, some leakages were observed at the dump valve.

The RWT was filled to capacity and body inspection was conducted for possible leakage. With the 0.5hp pump connected, water in the RWT was emptied. The time was noted and recorded. The above procedure was repeated thrice and the average time it took to empty the RWT was computed as 10.11 minutes.

The EWP was extended from the lowest to the maximum height and the various heights were measured from ground level as shown in Table (2).

CONCLUSION

Design and Development of the Gravity Evacuation Toilet Bowser saw some difficulties; however, the task of obtaining local, simpler and more efficient mechanism that operated on the principle of gravity evacuation of human wastes for commuter aircrafts was eventually accomplished.

Generally speaking, the toilet bowser combines good low profile lavatory system with simplicity in manufacture, low maintenance costs, long unit lifetime, and hygienic operator's environment. The EWP was made adjustable for the purpose of serving different types of commuter aircrafts depending on the height of their toilet outlets.

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